

Luffa Echinata Roxb. (devdali) A Mystical Traditional Herbal Drug Helps to Cure Specific Ailments

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Abstract

Luffa echinata commonly known as "devdali" and giant milkweed. It is a perennial herb of cucurbitaceae family. It is found in Rajasthan, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh in Indian region where highly rich biodiversity is found. There are many differences between a drug and a Divya Aushadhi. The same herb or other drug is a drug in normal state, but when it is used in a specific systematic method, it produces divine and proven effects by mantras ॐ अमृतगणरुद्रगणान्ताय स्वाहा । ॐ अमृतं कुरु कुरु अमृतेश्वराय स्वाहा ॥ At the end of a lunar or solar eclipse, on a full moon day, on the thirteenth day or the fifth day of the dark fortnight or on any auspicious day or auspicious constellation. The hardness and ability of the plant to survive in dry conditions makes it a valuable species in drought conditions.

The specific secondary metabolites are developed in the specific period or time of the day as well in the particular part of the plant viz. root, stem, leaves and the flowering parts develop the specific active constituents in the particular time.

In Hindu mythology the plant is often associated with spiritual purity and in ancient times it was associated with the gods. Its leaves, flowers and latex are used in traditional medicine to treat various ailments such as skin diseases, some diseases caused by Vata, Pitta, Kapha separately, two doshas, all tri-doshas, mixed diseases and incurable diseases, respiratory problems and digestive problems. It helps in the eye diseases, to assure in the sex determination, sperm count is increased by using the plant part. Devdali and Nirgundi together help in helps as antiaging. The procurement and fruitful utility is based on the relations between plant and human, the time of harvesting, plant part, storage conditions as well as processing.

Divya Aushdhi, Devdali, Vat, Pitta, Kapha.

Keywords

Introduction

Luffa echinata Roxb. plant is also known as Devdali. It is a perennial species. It had significant cultural, medicinal, and ecological importance. In the Hindu mythology the plant is often associated with spiritual purity and is linked to deities in ancient times. Its leaves, flowers, and latex are used in traditional medicine for treating in different ailments i.e. skin diseases, respiratory problems, and digestive issues. The plant's hardness and ability in arid conditions make to a valuable species in drought condition. The plant contains toxic compounds that necessitate careful handling, particularly in medicinal uses. This abstract explores the multifaceted role of the Devdali Kalp plant, focusing on its cultural significance, ecological value, and the challenges surrounding its medicinal uses, while highlighting the need for further research to maximize its benefits safely.

In India, the plant is generally found in the western and central regions, including Rajasthan, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Uttar Pradesh, as well as along the coastal areas. It is also found in parts of Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka. The plant prefers sunny, open areas, and its ability to endure extreme temperatures makes it a common sight in rural areas and on the edges of agricultural fields. (Kumar et al 2023 & 2024)

Luffa echinata belong to the family cucurbitaceae. It is an Ayurvedic medicinal plant which had been used a variety of symptoms of medicine in traditional system because it has active constituents like as cucurbitacin, saponin, echinatin, β -Sitosterol, oleanolic acid and flavonoids. This had important pathophysiological effects on the human body.

In this paper, Divine experiments of Devdali herb have been described. The description of the effects of these experiments is astonishing. It describes amazing miraculous yoga's. The texts are full of such yoga's which are used even today in villages by those who know the science of Shabar. The miraculous effect of these methods is proven. Therefore, the statements of these verses should not be disbelieved. In Rakshasa culture, health, wealth, strength are used for pleasure, the purpose of divine medicinal yogas is to make men and women young, powerful, beautiful and enjoy divine life. They have been discussed in this form. These divine yogas are miraculous. They endow one with in human power. Divine radiance and divine joy fill the body & mind. But some things are not mentioned in the Grantha.

To get the benefit from these yogas, first **Sankalp and Initiation**, then **Atonement** (of previous deeds), then **Snehan Sanskar** is done. After snehana, **Purgation** is done, then **Ubtan** and then **Swedana**. Divya yoga gives the desired benefits only when it is done by properly purifying the body and mind by the following prescribed methods.

Objective of study

1. To find out the difference between crude drug and mystical drug.
2. To find out the different methods of using Kalpa and its importance.
3. To find out the Divine Yoga's that produce astonishing effects on the human body.
4. To survey the herbal plant in the previous literatures for the future plan.

Review of Literature

In Ayurveda it is also known by different names e.g. Turangika, Devtandi, Kantaphala, Koshvrutta, Jeemutaka, Devdali, etc. Plants were collected from different regions of Baghpat district and Delhi NCR Region. (**Hooker 1879, Cooke 1967, Shah 1978**) described flower species are white and not yellow. **Singh et al., (2001)** observed *Luffa echinata* from Maharashtra had yellow flowers. Whereas white flowers of this species showed by previous authors. Populations studied presently also had snow- white flowers. **Hooker (1879)** observed on *Luffa echinata* Young fruit/ ovary is present and anthers distinct (5) at maturity. **Kirtikar and Basu (1918)** did the work on the Anthers are given orally to facilitate delivery; root strengthens muscles of neck and is tonic for hairs, laxative, analgesic, cures tumors and vaginal discharges. **Nigam & Pandya (1949)** observed on Chemistry of the plant. **Bapat and Chandra (1968), Lauria et al. (1976), Vaidya et al (1976)** observed on Hepato protective activity of fruits has been studied extensively. **Vaidya et al (1976)** Clinical trials have shown that serum bilirubin gets significantly reduced within 2 – 7 days when the drug was administered as nasal drops. **Jain (1991)** did the work on the whole plant and observed that it is used as blood purifier, fruits are used in dropsy and inflammatory piles, fruit powder snuffed in jaundice; leaves used in Dysentery and seed oil in skin diseases . **Jain et al., (1991)** observed that it is also used as anthelmintic, emetic and purgative. it also used in bronchitis, cholera, colic and urinary trouble **Kumar et al (2000)** worked on the antioxidant property of whole plant. **Singh et al., (2001)** showed distributional records its migration from Gujrat to Maharashtra like Mumbai and Pune. **Rastogi and Melhotra (1999, 2002, 2004, 2005)** did the work on the threatened species in Bihar. The whole plant is generally used in treatment of diabetes. **Khare (2007)** also has reported the 50 % ethanolic extract to exhibit hypoglycemic activity. **Ali Ajmal (2010)** observed that the whole plant is crushed in to fine powder and 1 teaspoon is given with water twice a day for treatment of diabetes. **Karodpati et al., (2011) and Kamble et al., (2013)** give the distributional reports & continuously published that floristic explorations are continuously made in different regions of all states. The distribution of ephemerals and seasonal *Luffa echinata* Roxb. was previously reported to Bengal (**Hooker 1879**), Gujarat (**Cooke, 1967**), Bihar and Orissa (**Haines 1921**) and Andhra Pradesh (**Pullaiah 1997**). **Bhogaonkar P Y and Dhole P A (2014)** worked on the New Distributional Record for *Luffa echinata* Roxb Vidarbha (Maharashtra).**Kashyap et al(2007)** explained about the herbal plants cultivation practice.

Methodology

Method of using Kalpa

These medicines should be used sequentially considering the time and fire in diseases caused by Vata, Pitta, Kapha separately, two doshas, all three doshas, mixed diseases and incurable diseases.

Properties of drug kalpa

The first kalpa kalpa of the drug has all the properties, the second kalpa churna has less properties than the first, the third kalpa rasa has quick-acting properties, the fourth kalpa oil is not defective. The fifth kalpa ark is devoid of all defects and illuminates groups of properties.

Effective method of collection which makes the medicine a Divine medicine

Generally it is related to the collection of plants. Plants are living beings. They have the same process of fear etc. as we have. When we uproot, break or cut them without any method, they get afflicted with fear. We all know that as soon as 'fear' arises, the energy level of the body falls to the lowest level. The plant parts collected at this time do not have any power (strength). The energy which produces a divine effect is not there in them. We can only get the benefit of their stored elements (Ali et al 2022.)

The traditional method of harvesting & procurement

1. The plant, creeper, shrub or tree is worshipped a day before.
2. Its root is cleaned and water of worship is poured. Due to this, the plant does not have any fear of getting any harm from that person. It becomes cheerful. Due to this the energetic level increases.
3. At such a time, if the branch, leaves, bark or root is obtained in one go with a benevolent attitude, the divine power of that plant remains in it.
4. If it is held with a cloth hand, brought and placed on a dry board, then washed with special substances and dried in the shade, then even after being eroded, its divine effect remains more than half.
5. The feeling while sowing, cutting, bringing or storing the plant also has a special effect. That is why the effect of the plant obtained with the chanting of mantras and devotion is extremely divine.
6. By treating the seed or seeds of the medicine with various types of botanical and organic juices and metallic juices, special qualities are produced in it.
7. After this, the method and yoga (along with the medicines) also produce divine effects.
8. The condition and type of fire also have an effect on the medicines which are cooked. For example, if a divine effect is produced by the stump of a wild cow and one gram of its fire, then that divine effect will not be produced by the stump of a domesticated cow. Here, it is not only the difference in temperature that is effective, the thing that is burning has the most important effect.
9. The vessel also has an effect. The use of ghee-filled earthen vessel, new earthen vessel, golden vessel, silver vessel, bronze vessel, copper vessel etc. produces divine effects in the respective places.
10. The effect of medicines also varies depending on the country (region). Dry region, cold region, rainy region, sea region, mountain region, Himalayan region etc. also produce difference in the quality and strength of medicines.
11. Apart from this, the form of consuming the medicine (i.e. paste, decoction, juice, oil, extract form), the time of consumption, the quantity of the medicine also has an effect.
12. The most effective of these is the purification of the body's system, purification of the mind, abstinence and diet-life.

This part includes the use of divine medicines, all these facts are given in the processes, it should be remembered that the divine effects are produced by the systematic approved methods. Sometimes it does not happen and sometimes it can be harmful due to not observing abstinence.

Divya Aushadhi

There are many differences between a drug and a Divya Aushadhi. The same herb or other drug is a drug in normal state, but when it is used in a specific systematic method, it produces divine and proven effects. Elements of Divya Prayog-

1. There is a difference in the properties and strengths of the drugs according to the difference in place.
2. There is also a difference in the properties and strengths of the drugs according to the difference in time (day-night).
3. There is also a difference in the properties and strengths of the drugs according to the difference in the constellations.
4. There is also a difference in the effect of the drugs according to the method of collecting the drugs.

Rasa : Katu (Pungent), Tikta (Bitter), Guna : Laghu (Light for digestion), Ruksha (Cause dryness), Virya : Ushna (hot in potency), Vipaka : Katu (Undergoes Pungent taste after digestion), Karma : Tridosahara (Pacifies all the dosha), Vamaka (Induces Emesis), Vishagna (Controls the poisonous effect). Whenever it is used in a specific prescribed

ethnic method, it produces the divine and proven effects by mantras ॐ अमृतगणरुद्रगणान्ताय स्वाहा । ॐ अमृतं कुरु कुरु अमृतेश्वराय स्वाहा ॥ At the end of a lunar or solar eclipse, on a full moon day, on the thirteenth day or the fifth day of the dark fortnight or on any auspicious day or auspicious constellation it has more effect. The hardness and ability of the plant to survive in dry conditions makes it a valuable species in drought conditions.

Plant's Potential Values

A number of pharmaceutical manufacturing concerns and classical preparations are made by *Luffa echinata*. Some examples are: Kustha, Sotha, Kasa, Antrasula, Suryavarta, Arsa, Svayathu (odema), Prameha (urinary disorders), Pilahayakritroga (hepato splenic infections).

An alcoholic extract of its dried leaves has strong local anesthetic property. It inhibits salivary secretion induced by pilocarpine. Vasinine, bronchodilatory stimulant, slightly hypotensive, uterine stimulant and abortifacient activity similar to that of oxytocin and methergine. Uterine stimulant action was seen on human myometrium. The utero- tonic and abortifacient active. It may be used during pregnancy for abortive.

Its antiseptic and spermatocidal character is essential oil present in leaves. *Luffa echinata* is highly active against amlapitta, pyorrhea, local bleeding and gums (teeth). The fresh leaves juice may be used in tuberculosis. It cures in vomiting, thirst, fever, neuralgia, dermatitis, tonsils, throat soar diphtheria, peptide ulcer & piles. It is also used in Rhinitis means loss of taste and smell due to swollen of nose, throat, mouth and tongue and all feel dry.

The Research Area

The proposed study research area is the Delhi NCR Region which has the major Geographical areas included agricultural region of NCT Delhi, Ghaziabad, Baghpat, Meerut, Hapur, Bulandshar and some areas of Haryana from North latitude 28°44'42"N and East longitude 77°05'35"E. This is highly developing area in the urbanization. It is depleting the herbal plants from the list of dominating medicinal plants. The samples and the survey was also done near the unstressed areas like hill stations which are free from transportation and industries.

Findings

This traditional medicinal herb helps to treat the skin diseases which are caused by Vata, Pitta, Kapha. Some incurable diseases of respiratory problems and digestive problems are cured. It helps in the eye diseases also. A specific characteristic is seen through literature and ethnobotanical survey with experiments assured in the sex determination and sperm counts are increased by using the Panchang.

Conclusion

Herbal medicines have been used for thousands of years to care for human health, but the safety of herbs is a myth today. Some people experience adverse effects from herbal medicines due to a variety of reasons, the main ones being lack of time and knowledge for collection, poor quality of medicines and unavailability of divine medicines, which leads to low or no efficacy of the medicine. The increasing use of herbal remedies requires scientifically sound evidence for the principles behind the treatments and the effectiveness of the medicine. Various parts of the *Luffa echinata* plant have been found to have antioxidant, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antidepressant, anxiolytic, antiepileptic, hepatoprotective, antibacterial, antifungal, antiulcer and anticancer properties. Ethnomedicinal uses and pharmacological studies confirm the therapeutic value of *Luffa echinata*. Very little is known about the clinical toxicity and phyto-analytical properties of this plant. Many phytochemical studies have been reported but modern tools are still needed for better understanding of phytochemical analysis. Availability of information on ethnomedicinal uses, active phytochemicals present and medicinal approaches will help in scientifically exploring it and also help in establishing and validating the quality and practice of this herbal medicine at present. The real link with the literature review and in the future research work it will be helpful.

In the previous studies the herb is used to for tradition man and in the Hindu Granths as in Rawan Samhita it is depicted as a specific prescribed ethnic method, it produces the divine and proven effects by mantras ॐ अमृतगणरुद्रगणान्ताय स्वाहा । ॐ अमृतं कुरु कुरु अमृतेश्वराय स्वाहा ॥ At the end of a lunar or solar eclipse, on a full moon day, on the thirteenth day or the fifth day of the dark fortnight or on any auspicious day or auspicious constellation it has more effect. The herb is described by Haines (1921) noted in flora of Orissa, Cooke (1967) noted in the flora of the Presidency of Bombay, Kritiker & Basu (1918) described in Indian medicinal plants the same plant. In the present studies the same plant has some qualities as some depictions in the ancient literatures about the results of the sex determiner chromosome and sperm counts. Normally the root tips and flowering bud tips cells are divided at the peeping of the day due to the IR, UV and Short waves of the light.

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